

ISic1531

I.Sicily inscription 1531

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 14482

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [ζήσασα ἔτη]
2. εἴκοσι ἐτελεύτησ
3. εν χρησιανή
4. ἀναγνος ἀναχώρι

Apparatus

Text of IG

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492643

EDCS 39102170

PHI 140494

PHI 140497

Bibliography

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